

KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDE, AND PRACTICES REGARDING EVIDENCE BASE PRACTICES OF NURSES: A CROSS-SECTIONAL STUDY IN A PRIVATE HOSPITAL, PESHAWAR

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ABSTRACT

Background: Evidence-based practices are considered the most important element to improve health services and achieve positive patient outcomes (1). Evidence-based practices help the nurse to find effective treatment techniques and also greatly influence the nursing skill, making better decisions, informing action that has the desired impact.

Objective: The objective of the study is to evaluate the knowledge, attitude, and practices of nurses towards evidence-based practice in NWGH and NWTW.

Methods: The nonprobability convenience sampling technique is utilized to select participants due to its feasibility, allowing for to choice of participants based on ease and accessibility. Data was collected from 184 samples of nurses working in Northwest General and Northwest Teaching Hospital, through adopted and pre-structured questionnaires. Incorporating a dichotomous scale (YES and NO). This consists of 27 closed-ended questions.

Results: The result of this study revealed that knowledge regarding EBP had the highest mean score (1.2038), followed by practice (1.385875), then attitude (1.10446). And also that (63.0%) of the nurses had a good knowledge, and (37.0%) had a bad knowledge regarding Evidence-based practice. Moreover, (70.1%) had a good attitude and (29.9%) had a bad attitude towards Evidence-based practice. And in the area of practice, 63.6% had a good practice and 36.4% had a bad practice in Evidence-based practice.

Conclusion: The current study provides the hospital managers and educators with essential information on how to improve and enhance the nurses' application and performance in EBP among nurses. The finding suggested that knowledge in EBP ranked the highest mean score, followed by practice, and then attitude. We also conclude that nurses' attitude toward EBP is affected by workload and the shortage of time. Moreover, regardless of having an abundance of knowledge regarding EBP, there is a need for enhancement of their capacity to retrieve information on EBP, and nurses face difficulty in practicing EBP.

Keywords: Knowledge, attitude, practice, nurses, and evidence-based practice.

Introduction

Evidence-based practice in nursing refers to the approach of making clinical decisions and providing

patient care based on the best available evidence from up-to-date research, nurses' clinical expertise, and patient preferences and values(2). Evidence-

based practice has its origin in the work of Florence Nightingale in the 1800s and has advanced since then in both medical and nursing disciplines(3). History shows that EBP has been used in Nursing for decades. Florence Nightingale, after her return from the Crimean War, recognized the importance of systematic data collection. She worked along with sanitary experts, including social statistician William Farr, to identify the Cause of high mortality(4). This showed the importance of data collection and analysis in bringing change. In the 1860 International Statistical Congress, she advocated for the collection of hospital statistics to ease comparisons of results between hospitals, regions, and countries(5). This laid the beginning for the International Classification of Diseases (ICD) code, which is still in practice. Her enthusiasm towards using public policy decisions and advocating for health and housing questions in the 1861 census formed the base for modern epidemiology and data-driven decision-making in public health(6). While research strongly supports the positive influence of evidence-based practice in nursing, it is still underutilized in nursing due to a lack of professional values and expertise in its implementation(7). The purpose of the study is to measure the nurses' knowledge and attitude towards evidence-based practices. Evidence-based practices help the nurse find effective treatment techniques. Evidence-based practices greatly influence nursing skills, making better decisions, and informing action that has the desired impact(8). EBP has directed the knowledge and practice of nurses, and how they care for patients(9). Before EBP, patient care was deliberately shaped by the circumstances and judgments of those providing care. With time, EBP has played a role in shifting from traditional and self-assured opinion to using facts and figures obtained from valid research and studies. Furthermore, studies show that nurses practicing EBP enhance the effectiveness of patient care as compared to traditional practice(10). Studies show that nurses have an abundance of knowledge regarding EBP and its advantages in patient care. But, they also find it back-breaking and challenging to implement these clinical practices. Moreover, nurses may hold positive attitudes toward research but lack knowledge, training, and confidence in

their ability to conduct research(11). An evidence-based approach to decision-making is based on a combination of using critical thinking and the best available evidence(12). Nurses of the 21st century are battling countless challenges like, lack of knowledge and compliance with evidence-based practice, understanding, and attitude toward research. A study conducted by the National Board of Health and Welfare in Sweden showed that 8.6% of hospital patients were injured during care. These preventable injuries were avoidable if genuine knowledge had been applied(13). Moreover, a study conducted by the Rehman College of Nursing in Pakistan revealed that, even though Evidence-based practice is considered a key skill for Nurses and other healthcare providers, it is still low in practice by the RNs. Strategies are needed to enhance the knowledge, practice, and skills of RNs. Lack of self-determination, time, and cooperative administration are the main barriers to Evidence-based practices. Strategies should be made to solve these issues to make the application of Evidence-based practices easier for nurses(14). The main focus of this study is to explore the knowledge, attitudes, and practices. This study will help the hospital administration for the promotion of health and positive outcomes for the patients while working based on evidence-based practice. And it will also help bring positive changes to the evidence-based practice of nurses working in NWGH and NWTH. The study will also explore a better understanding of barriers faced by nurses in applying evidence-based practice(15).

Methods:

This is a quantitative cross-sectional study. To evaluate the knowledge, attitude, and practice of nurses toward evidence-based practice. This study was conducted in Northwest General Hospital and Northwest Teaching Hospital, located in phase-5 Hayatabad, Peshawar. We were analyzing the knowledge, attitude, and practice of nurses regarding evidence-based practice. The overall duration of our research study was 6months. Those nurses who have more than six months of clinical experience were included in this research study, and those nurses who have more than six months of clinical experience but have taken a course on EBP

in the past three months are excluded from our study. The sample size of 184 nurses from NWGH and NWTW was calculated through the Raosoft calculator, with a confidence level of 95% with a margin of 5% error. And the total number of populations is 350(16). The nonprobability convenience sampling technique is utilized to select participants due to its feasibility, allowing for to choice of participants based on ease and accessibility. The data was collected through adopted and pre-structured questionnaires. A defined questionnaire was given to concerned candidates at NWGH and NWTW. This questionnaire consists of two parts; the first portion consists of demographic data, including age, qualification, experience, and current working unit. The second portion consists of knowledge, attitude, and practice of nurses toward evidence-based practice, which consists of 27 closed-ended questions. The knowledge portion consists of 10 items, while the attitude and practice portions consist of 8 and 8 items, respectively(17). Before the data collection, informed written consent will be signed by the participant. The Data were analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences SPSS software, version 28). The data was presented using descriptive statistics. The demographic variable was summarized by mean, median, and proportion. While other variables, including

knowledge, attitude, and practice) was analyzed by frequency, percentage, and a table. Ethical approval was taken from GC, IRB, and ERB (NWCN/Research/2023/636). Permission was taken from the Northwest Institute of Health Sciences and Northwest General and Teaching Hospital. Consent was obtained from all participants. Nurses understood all aspects before participating that there was no risk or harm in this research study, as well as that all the data were kept under lock.

Result

4:1 Demographic characteristics of the Nurses:

The research included a total of 184 participants affiliated with Northwest General and Northwest Teaching Hospital.

Among 184 participants, 101(54.9%) were male and 83(45.1%) were female. The mean age score was 26.63 years (range 22-40 years). And the majority (62.5%) had BSN qualification, while (16.3%) have Post RN qualification and (21.1%) are diploma holders. The majority (57.1%) of the sample had (1-2 years) of work experience, the other (38.6%) had an experience of (3-5 years), and the rest (4.3%) had an experience of (6 years and above). All of them had a Private Job (100%), it was because the study setting was at 2 Private hospitals. [Table 1]

Table 1: Characteristics of Nurses working at Northwest General and Northwest Teaching Hospitals who completed the questionnaire (N=184)

Characteristics	Entire sample (N=184) mean ± SD	(N=184) mean ± SD Entire sample (N=184) n(%)
Age (years)	26.63 ± 2.983	
Gender		
Male		101(54.9%)
Female		83(45.1%)
Work experience	1.4728 ± 5814	
1-2 years		105(57.1%)
3-5 years		71(38.6%)
6 < years		8(4.3)
Qualification		

BSN	115(62.5%)
Post-RN	30(16.3%)
MSN	----
Diploma	39(21.2%)

Percentage-wise distribution of staff nurses

The different ages of nurse participants. In this study, the age range from 20- 25 is about 33.3%, age from 26-30 is 48.6%, age from 31-35 is 13.9%, and from 36-40 is about 1.4%.

Percentage-wise distribution of gender

The response of participants is 100%. And the graph reveals that it consists of a (54.9%) male and

(45.1%) female ratio.

Distribution of nurses according to work experience

The study reveals that 57.1% of participants have a work experience of 1-2 years, the other 38.6% have an experience of 3-5 years, and the rest 4.3% have an experience of 6 years and above. **Table 2.**

Table 2: Work experience

YEAR	FREQUENCY	PERCENT	VALID PERCENT	CUMULATIVE PERCENT
1-2	105	57.1	57.1	57.1
3-5	77	38.6	38.1	95.7
ABOVE 6	8	4.3	4.3	100
TOTAL	184	100	100	

Distribution according to qualification

The study reveals that about 62.5% of the sample have a BSN qualification, about 16.3% have a Post

RN qualification, and 21.1% are diploma holders. **Table 3.**

Table 3. Qualification

EDUCATION	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
BSN	115	62.5	62.5	62.5
Post RN	30	16.3	16.3	78.8
Diploma Nursing	39	21.2	21.2	100
Total	100	100	100	

The result of this study revealed that knowledge regarding EBP had the highest mean score (1.2038), followed by practice (1.385875), then attitude (1.10446)

Knowledge of the Nurses regarding Evidence-based practice

Among 27 questions, 10 questions were from the knowledge area. (100%) Respondents answered all the questions. (63.0%) had a good knowledge and (37.0%) had a bad knowledge regarding Evidence-based practice. **Table 4.**

Table 4. Knowledge

No.	Question	Yes n (%)	No n (%)
1	Knowledge of the importance of assessing patients as per evidence-based protocol	177 (96.2%)	7 (3.8%)
2	Conversion of information into research questions	149 (81.0%)	35 (19.0%)
3	Sharing information and new ideas with colleagues	165 (89.7%)	19 (10.3%)
4	Belief that EBP leads to favorable patient outcomes	154 (83.7%)	30 (16.3%)
5	Knowledge about the improvement of evidence-based practice	142 (77.2%)	42 (22.8%)
6	Belief that nurses should update their knowledge regarding EBP	146 (79.3%)	38 (20.7%)
7	Ability to determine the validity of evidence	131 (71.2%)	53 (28.8%)
8	Identification of gaps in nursing practice	145 (78.8%)	39 (21.2%)
9	Critical analysis of EBP against set standards	132 (71.7%)	52 (28.3%)
10	Knowledge of retrieving information and evidence	124 (67.4%)	60 (32.6%)

Attitude of nurses regarding Evidence-based practice

Among 27 questions, 8 questions were from the attitude area. (100%) Respondents answered all the

questions. (70.1%) had a good attitude and (29.9%) had a bad attitude towards evidence-based practice.

Table 5

Table 5. attitude

No.	Question	Yes n (%)	No n (%)
11	Belief that evidence-based practice is fundamental to professional practice	160 (87.0%)	24 (13.0%)
12	Changing practice when evidence is found	160 (87.0%)	24 (13.0%)
13	Belief that workload is the main barrier to evidence-based practice	155 (84.2%)	29 (15.8%)

14	Need support from the higher authority to remove barriers	128 (69.6%)	56 (30.4%)
15	Having sufficient time to read relevant literature	115 (62.5%)	69 (37.5%)
16	Belief that nurses have enough authority to change patient care based on evidence	136 (73.9%)	48 (26.1%)
17	Marking a question from own clinical practice	128 (69.6%)	56 (30.4%)
18	Researching reports/articles available	133 (72.3%)	51 (27.7%)

Practice of nurses regarding Evidence-based practice

Among 27 questions, 9 questions were from the

practice area. (100%) Respondents answered all the questions. (63.6%) had a good practice and (36.4%) had a bad practice in Evidence-based practice. [Table 6]

Table 6.

NO	Question	Response	n(%)
19	Do you evaluate the outcome of your own practice?	Yes	145(78.8%)
		No	39(21.2%)
20	Did you integrate evidence with expertise?	Yes	142(77.2%)
		No	42(22.8%)
21	Do you formulate clearly answerable questions to fill the gap?	Yes	140(76.1%)
		No	44(23.9%)
22	Did you feel difficulty in providing nursing care on EBP?	Yes	138(75.0%)
		No	46(25.0%)
23	Do you read nursing literature on EBP?	Yes	135(73.4%)
		No	49(26.6%)
24	Do you assess patients on evidence-based practice guideline	Yes	149(81.0%)

	protocol?	No	35(19.0%)
25	Did you apply an intervention based on the most applicable evidence?	Yes	146(79.3%)
		No	38(20.7%)
26	Did you evaluate your intervention and identify the area of improvement?	Yes	129(70.1%)
		No	55(29.9%)
27	Do you share your information with colleagues?	Yes	148(80.4%)
		No	36(19.6%)

Table 7: Descriptive Statistics of Knowledge, Attitude, and Practice (n = 184)

Statistics	Knowledge	Attitude	Practice
Valid (N)	184	184	184
Missing	0	0	0
Mean	12.04	9.94	11.09
Std. Error of Mean	0.10	0.09	0.11
Median	12.00	10.00	11.00
Mode	12.00	10.00	11.00
Std. Deviation	1.40	1.22	1.53
Variance	1.95	1.50	2.33
Range	6.00	6.00	7.00
Minimum	10.00	8.00	9.00
Maximum	16.00	14.00	16.00
Sum	2215.00	1829.00	2040.00
50th Percentile	12.00	10.00	11.00

Table 7 presents the descriptive statistics of knowledge, attitude, and practice (KAP) scores among the study participants. A total of 184 valid responses were analyzed for each variable, with no missing data, indicating complete participation and reliable data Collection.

The mean knowledge score was 12.04 ± 1.40 , with scores ranging from 10 to 16. The median and mode were both 12, suggesting a symmetrical distribution of knowledge scores and indicating that most participants demonstrated a moderate to high level of knowledge. The relatively low standard deviation reflects limited variability, meaning

knowledge levels were fairly consistent across participants.

For attitude, the mean score was 9.94 ± 1.22 , with values ranging between 8 and 14. The median and mode were both 10, showing that the majority of respondents held a generally positive attitude. The variance and range indicate moderate dispersion, suggesting some variability in attitudes but overall clustering around the central value.

Discussion

The study revealed that among 184 participants, 101(54.9%) were male and 83(45.1%) were female. The mean age score was 26.63 years (range 22-40

years). And the majority (62.5%) had BSN qualification, while (16.3%) have Post RN qualification and (21.1%) are diploma holders. The majority (57.1%) of the sample had (1-2 years) of work experience, the other (38.6%) had an experience of (3-5 years), and the rest (4.3%) had an experience of (6 years or above). All of them had a Private Job (100%), it was because the study setting was at 2 Private hospitals.

This study focused specifically on describing the knowledge, attitude, and practice of nurses working in NWGH and NWTH. The result of this study revealed that knowledge regarding EBP had the highest mean score (1.2038) (63.0% had good knowledge regarding EBP), followed by practice (1.385875) (63.3% had good practice in EBP) and then attitude (1.10446) (70.1% had a good attitude towards EBP). This means nurses are practicing and have knowledge regarding EBP. However, their mean score of attitude toward EBP was less than the other 2 aspects. The 2nd question asked. (Q12: Do you change practice when you find evidence?) was marked yes by 160(87.0%) proving that the attitude of nurses is positive towards evidence based practice, But From the same table the Question 13 (Do you believe that work load is the main barrier to evidence base practice?) we learned that the reason for less mean score of attitude toward EBP is work load out of 184 respondent 155(84.2%) marked yes. And 128(69.6%) of respondents marked yes on question 14 Do you need support from a higher authority to remove these barriers? 128 nurses out of 184 think that they need support from a higher authority to remove the barrier (which is workload), and also Q15 revealed that 69(37.5%) nurses don't have time to read relevant literature. In [Table 4 Knowledge] the first question asked was (Q1: Do you know the importance of assessing patient as per evidence base protocol?) to that (177 that is 96.2%) nurses responded yes proving that majority of nurses knows Evidence-based practice, but they don't know how to retrieve information on Evidence-based practice as revolved by Q10: Do you know how to retrieve information and evidence?) where 60(32.6%) of the sample marked NO, showing that they don't know how to retrieve information on evidence-based practice.

And we learn from [Table 6 Practice] (Q24: Do you assess patients on evidence-based practice guideline protocol?) that nurses at Northwest General and Northwest Teaching Hospital practice according to Evidence-based Practices, to Q24, [149(81.0%)] responded with a Yes!. But the response to (Q22: Did you feel difficulty in providing nursing care on EBP?) shows that about 138(75.0%) of nurses feel difficulty in providing EBP care.

The same study was conducted in Jordan, consisting of 500 sample of nurses, the majority (58.0%) of whom were female, and the majority (87%) were BS holders. The study indicated that the attitude (4.07)(2.8%) of nurses towards EBP has the highest mean score, followed by (3.99) (47.5%) knowledge and practice (3.84) (42%) left which scored the least mean score. In this study the most important learning need in the attitude area was that about (3.73 mean score) (34%) nurse marked yes to the [Q: My workload is too great for me to keep up to date with all the new evidence], in the knowledge the lowest mean score (3.36) (22.8) was given to "skills in research". While in the practice area, the lowest (3.60) (13.4%) mean score was given to "formulated a clearly answerable question as the beginning of the process towards filling this gap"(18).

The same study was also conducted in Malawi, consisting of 208 sample size the response rate was 87.9%. The majority (79.2%) of respondents were females, with 20.8% males. (78.7%) Of the sample had a BS degree. (78.7%) The majority had 5 years of work experience. In this study, 7 7-point Likert scale was used, while in our study Dichotomous scale ("yes" or "no") was used. This study was conducted to reveal the knowledge, attitude, and practice of nurses and midwives regarding Evidence-based practice in Malawi. Disclosing that the highest mean score was in the attitude area (4.85±1.92 to 6.16±2.9), followed by knowledge (4.34±1.53 to 5.46±1.49), while practice being the lowest (3.56±1.9 to 3.85±1.7), in this study the lowest and negative mean score (4.85) for attitude was on the question (Table 2: Q Attitudes Making time in a work schedule for research). The lowest mean score for knowledge was in the area Converting information needs into research questions (4.11), Research skills (4.34), IT skills (4.53), and Awareness of major information types/sources

(4.57). And the highest area for knowledge was (5.46±1.49) for sharing ideas and information with colleagues, in the practice aspects, almost all the areas were marked low, but the lowest (3.56) was in “critically appraising literature”(19)(20).

Conclusion

The current study provides the hospital managers and educators with essential information on how to improve and enhance the nurses’ application and performance in EBP among nurses.

The finding suggested that knowledge in EBP ranked the highest mean score, followed by practice, and then attitude. We also conclude that nurses’ attitude toward EBP is affected by workload and the shortage of time. Moreover, regardless of having an abundance of knowledge regarding EBP, there is a need for enhancement of their capacity to retrieve information on EBP, and nurses face difficulty in practicing EBP.

Limitations

This study only included the private hospitals. This study is only about nurses, being biased and not including the other medical staff in the study.

Strengths

The study involves not just knowledge but also attitude and practice regarding EBP.

The study also emphasized the importance of EBP in patient care and the professional growth of nurses.

Recommendations

Based on the results of the study, these recommendations were made.

Methods should be used to reduce nurses' load.

Seminars should be arranged on the importance of EBP. And on where to find the latest evidence-based studies

Nurses should be provided with the most advanced equipment to make their work less back-breaking.

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